

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 5

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович

*PhD, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena

*DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович

*Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхиси кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор, Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Сандов Сандамир Аброрович

*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной
работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD кафедры онкологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой
хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического
госпиталю Сеульского национального университета,
Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и
эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры
акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович

PhD, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии
факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ.
Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой
акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой
диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета,
д.м.н., профессор, Душанбе, Таджикистан
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Саидов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский
фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический
медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna
PhD Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*PhD, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Shukrullayeva G.J., Axmedov A.A.**
THE CONDITION AND FEATURES OF HARD TISSUES OF TEETH DURING PREGNANCY.....10
2. **Vokhidov E.R.**
ASSESSMENT OF DENTAL STATUS AND ORAL HEALTH IN PREGNANT WOMEN.16
3. **Kuliev O.A., Karabaev A.G.**
PATHOGENETIC BASIS OF REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM DISORDERS IN THE POST-INTENSIVE CARE PERIOD.....21

THERAPY

4. **Musayeva L.J., Yakubov A.V., Zufarov P.S., Abdusamatova D.Z., Saidova Sh.A., Pulatova N.I.**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF REBAMIPID IN THE TREATMENT OF FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA.....26
5. **Yakubov A.V., Musayeva L.J., Akbarova D.S., Saidova Sh.A., Aripdjanova Sh.S., Avazova G.N.**
THE CURRENT ROLE OF MACROLYDES IN THE TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA.....31
6. **Khasanjanova F.O., Mamatova N.T.**
ASSESSMENT OF RENAL DYSFUNCTION IN YOUNG PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME AS AN INDEPENDENT PREDICTOR OF DISEASE PROGNOSIS.....37
7. **Makhmudova N.M.**
PHYTOTHERAPY OF DYSPEPTIC SYMPTOMS IN PATIENTS WITH H. PYLORI-ASSOCIATED CHRONIC GASTRITIS USING THE DIETARY SUPPLEMENT VENTRAP.....43

SURGERY

8. **Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Mukhiddinov B.X., Askarov P.A.**
ASSESSMENT OF RENAL DYSFUNCTION IN YOUNG PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME AS AN INDEPENDENT PREDICTOR OF DISEASE PROGNOSIS.....50
9. **Makhmudov T.B., Sherbekov U.A., Kurbaniazov Z.D.**
PROGNOSTIC FACTORS FOR CHOOSING THE VOLUME OF OPERATION IN TOXIC FORMS OF GOITER.....59
10. **Makhmudov T.B., Sherbekov U.A., Kurbaniazov Z.D.**
EFFICIENCY OF PLASMAPHORESIS IN PREOPERATIVE PREPARATION OF PATIENTS WITH SEVERE THYROTOXICOSIS.....69
11. **Mardonov B.A., Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Rakhmanov K.E.**
COMPLEXITY AND FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF POSTCHOLECYSTECTOMY SYNDROME.....78
12. **Egamberdiyev A.A.**
ENDOVIDEOSURGICAL METHODS FOR THE TREATMENT OF ESOPHAGEAL HIATAL HERNIAS.....84
13. **Abdullayev S.A., Xudoynazarov U.R., Boysariyev Sh.U.**
PROBLEMS OF TREATMENT OF PURULENT-INFLAMMATORY COMPLICATIONS OF SOFT TISSUES IN SINDROME DIABETES MELLITUS FUT.....89

14. **Daminov F.A., Bobokulov A.U.**
PATHOGENETIC ANALYSIS OF GASTRODUODENAL ULCER (LITERATURE REVIEW).....94
15. **Jurayev O.U., Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Khursanov Y.E.**
CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE VARICOTROMBOPHLEBITIS AND RESULTS RESEARCH VENOUS SYSTEMS LOWER LIMBS.....101
16. **Shonazarov I.Sh., Oblokulov Z.T.**
THE NATURE OF THE MICROFLORA OF THE ABDOMINAL CAVITY DEPENDING ON THE PH VALUES IN PERFORATED DUODENAL ULCER.....108
17. **Shonazarov I.Sh., Oblokulov Z.T.**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT TACTICS IN PATIENTS WITH PERFORATED DUODENAL ULCER.....113
18. **Raxmatov B.X., Xujabaev S.T.**
CHOICE OF SURGICAL INTERVENTION IN CHRONIC HAEMORRHOIDS.....122
19. **Raxmatov B.X., Xujabaev S.T., Dusiyarov M.M.**
DYNAMICS OF THE WOUND PROCESS AFTER HAEMORRHOIDECTOMY.....126

PEDIATRICS

20. **Garifullina L.M.**
FEATURES OF FORMATION OF RISK FACTORS FOR THE EMERGENCE OF METABOLIC SYNDROME IN CHILDREN WITH ABDOMINAL OBESITY.....133
21. **Yuldashev B.A., Murodova M.D.**
SUBJECTIVE AND OBJECTIVE CLINICAL SYMPTOMS OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISORDERS IN CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....140
22. **Begnaeva M.U., Siddikov O.U.**
INCIDENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF DRUG POISONING IN CHILDREN.....146
23. **Ulugmuratov A.A.**
EFFECTIVENESS OF ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY FOR INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN.....152

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

24. **Ibragimov D.D., Boymuradov Sh.A., Baratova Sh.N.**
INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATING PATIENTS WITH COMBINED INJURIES OF FACIAL BONES WITH ASSESSMENT OF THE HYGIENIC CONDITION OF THE ORAL CAVITY.....156
25. **Islamova N.B.**
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF DENTAL REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH COMPLETE ADENTIA.....163
26. **Khanazarov D.A.**
ON THE ISSUE OF ODONTOPREPARATION IN ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY.....168

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

27. **Mirdjurayev E.M., Samiyev A.S., Bobomurodov G.A.**
INNOVATIVE METHODOS FOR REHABILITATION OF STROKE COMPLICATIONS.....178
28. **Muzaffarova N.Sh., Shirinov Sh.U.**
THE COURSE OF HEADACHE IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE.....183

29. **Xudaybergenov N.Y., Kilichev I.A., Adambaev Z.I., Samiyev A.S.**
INFLUENCE OF GEOMAGNETIC ACTIVITY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF BRAIN STROKES.....188
30. **Sabirov D.M., Eshonov O.Sh., Batirov U.B., Khaydarova S.E.**
MONITORING OF HEMATOLOGICAL INDICES IN PREDICTING OUTCOMES IN CEREBROVASCULAR CRITICAL CONDITIONS.....192
31. **Umirova S.M.**
CORRECTION OF DIABETIC POLYNEUROPATHY NIVALIN WITH PHARMACOPUNCTURE METHOD.....199
32. **Khakimova S.Z.**
REDUCING THE INTENSITY OF COMPLICATIONS WITH THE HELP OF REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....205
33. **Haydarova S. Kh., Sharipov R.Kh., Mavlyanova Z.F., Xudoyqulova F.**
FEATURES OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF LONG-TERM EFFECTS OF PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....210

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

34. **Lutfullaev U.L., Kobilova Sh.Sh., Safarova N.I., Madaminova N.E.**
PREDICTORS OF CLINICAL OUTCOME IN SENSORINEURAL HEARING LOSS.....219
35. **Lutfullaev U.L., Kobilova Sh.Sh., Safarova N.I., Madaminova N.E., Zoirov O.T., Buronov F.Y., Makhamov Kh.O.**
EFFECTIVENESS OF PROLONGED ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA.....226
36. **Raupova K.M., Nasretdinova M.T.**
PROFESSIONAL HARDNESS OF HEARING UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF THE STRONG INTERRUPTED NOISE.....235
37. **Nasretdinova M.T., Xayitov A.A., Dustboboyev D.S., Normurodov N.A.** MANAGEMENT OF OTITIS MEDIA WITH EFFUSION IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES.....241
38. **Nasretdinova M.T., Xayitov A.A., Dustboboyev D.S., Normurodov N.A.**
CHRONIC EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA IN CHILDREN: CYTOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CONFIRMATION OF STAGES OF THE DISEASE.....248
39. **Nasretdinova M.T., Omonova M.Sh.**
MICROFLORA IN CHRONIC POLYPOUS SINUSITIS.....255
40. **Nasretdinova M.T., Omonova M.Sh.**
MANAGEMENT OF CHRONIC POLYPOUS RHINOSINUSITIS.....261

ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY

41. **Boyko E.V., Tychiev A.P.**
RESULTS OF TRIMODAL THERAPY FOR INVASIVE BLADDER CANCER.....265
42. **Xamidov O.A.**
CURRENT STATE OF MEDICAL RADIOLOGY IN THE WORLD.....270
43. **Jumanov Z.E., Xamidov O.A., Beknazarova X.N.**
MODERN METHODS OF VISUALIZATION OF GALLBLADDER DISEASES.....295
44. **Raximov N.M, Shaxanova Sh.Sh, Raxmonov K.A.**
S100 PROTEIN EXPRESSION AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN DISSEMINATED BREAST CANCER.....302
45. **Urozov N.E., Vypova N.L., Nishanov D.A., Madaliyev A.A., Ibragimov Sh.N., Enikeeva Z.M.**
STUDY OF TOXICOLOGY OF THE ANTITUMOR DRUG KOLKHIPRIT-NEO (K-20).309

46. **Ulmasov F.G., Esankulova B.S.**
IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL STUDY OF THE OVARIAN CANCER
MICROENVIRONMENT AT DIFFERENT STAGES: THE ROLE OF IMMUNE CELLS IN
TUMOR PROGRESSION.....318
47. **Akramov A.R.**
DYNAMICS OF INCIDENCE, AGE AND MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES PRIMARY
BRAIN TUMORS ACCORDING TO THE DATA OF THE SAMARKAND BRANCH
RSSPMC ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY.....322

MORPHOLOGY

48. **Yusupova N.A., Oripov F.S.**
NON-INVASIVE DIAGNOSIS OF FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN THE GASTRIC UNDER
THE INFLUENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS.....328
49. **Kim T.A., Mavlyanova Z.F., Tastanova G.E.**
INSULIN-PRODUCING FUNCTION OF THE PANCREAS, LIPID PEROXIDATION
INDICATORS AND ANTIOXIDANT DEFENSE SYSTEMS IN RATS EXPOSED TO
LEAD.....336
50. **Zohidova S.H., Mamataliyev A.R.**
MORPHOLOGY OF EXTRAHEPATIC BILE DUCTS IN LABORATORY ANIMALS
AFTER EXPERIMENTAL REMOVAL OF THE GALLBLADDER.....340
51. **Khamidova F.M., Narzikulov Sh.F.**
MORPHORANGENOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INFLAMMATORY
PROCESSES OF THE RESPIRATORY ORGANS.....346
52. **Davronova M.Sh., Ilyasov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aytimova G.Y.**
INFLUENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS ON MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
THE PANCREAS.....358
53. **Khoshimov B.L., Akhmedova S.M.**
INFLUENCE OF METABOLIC SYNDROME ON ARTERIES.....363
54. **Babajanov T.Zh., Ilesov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aitimova G.Y.** IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL
ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES THAT DEVELOPED IN THE TISSUE
STRUCTURES OF THE DUODENUM UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF ENERGY
DRINKS.....375
55. **Babajanov T.Zh., Ilesov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aitimova G.Y.**
STUDY OF EFFECTS OF ENERGY DRINKS ON MORPHOLOGICAL AND
MORPHOMETRIC STATE OF DUODENAL TISSUE STRUCTURES IN RATS.....381
56. **Kurbanov G.T.**
PECULIARITIES OF THE ORGANIZATION AND STRUCTURE OF THE MAMMALIAN
RESPIRATORY TRACT.....388
57. **Juraev K.D., Islamov Sh.E.**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND PARAMETERS OF THE THYMUS
GLAND IN CHILDREN.....393
58. **Khasanova D.A., Azimova Z.S.**
FEATURES OF LUNG MORPHOLOGY UNDER INFLUENCE OF DYES AND ITS
PHYTCORRECTION.....401
59. **Samieva U. Gulnoza, Rakhmonov T. Sardor.**
PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF IRON DEFICIENCY IN HEART FAILURE.....411

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

60. **Nuritdinov U.A., Fattakhov R.A.**
ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH UNILATERAL ANTERIOR DISCLOSATION OF THE TMJ ARTICULAR DISC.....417

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

61. **Indiaminov S.I., Shoyimov Sh.U., Sagdullayev N.N.**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HEAD STRUCTURE INJURIES IN PEDESTRIANS INJURED AS A RESULT OF COLLISIONS WITH MOVING VEHICLES.....424

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

62. **Bustanov Sh.Y.**
ETIO-PATHO-MORPHOGENESIS OF COVID-19 (LITERATURE REVIEW).....429
63. **Adjablaeva N. Dinara, Parpieva N. Nargiza**
STRUCTURE OF SOMATIC PATHOLOGY FEATURES OF EPIDEMIOLOGICAL HISTORY DURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF LTBI AND ITS PROGRESSION IN CHILDREN.....438

UROLOGY

64. **Allazov I.S., Allazov S. A.**
CYSTIC KIDNEY NEOPLASMS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....447
65. **Allazov S.A., Allazov I.S.**
MODERN VIEWS ON DIAGNOSTIC METHODS AND TREATMENT OF URINARY PERITONITIS.....458

PHARMACOLOGY

66. **Kasimova D.S., Vladimir A.A., Babich S.M., Khamrakulov Sh.Kh.**
CHANGES IN THE DIGESTABILITY OF STARCH DURING INTERACTION WITH FATS IN THE COMPOSITION OF STARCH-FAT SUBSTRATES.....466
67. **Kasimova D.S., Vladimir A.A., Babich S.M., Khamrakulov Sh.Kh.**
INFLUENCE OF FAT HYDROLYSATES ON CHANGES IN THE DIGESTABILITY OF STARCH IN THE COMPOSITION OF STARCH- FAT SUBSTRATES.....474

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

UMIROVA Surayyo Mamurjonovna
PhD
Samarkand State Medical University

CORRECTION OF DIABETIC POLYNEUROPATHY NIVALIN WITH PHARMACOPUNCTURE METHOD

For citation: Umirova S.M. Correction of diabetic polyneuropathy nivalin with pharmacopuncture method // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 5, pp.199-204

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14181883>

ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to the correction of diabetic polyneuropathy by the method of pharmacopuncture - a method based on the introduction of medications into the area of reflexology points. Diabetic neuropathy, like diabetes itself, leads to significant changes in the life and health of patients. The formation of DPN is based on the progressive loss of myelinated fibers - segmental demyelination and axonal degeneration, as a result of which the processes of impulse transmission along the nerve fiber are disrupted. Hyperglycemia triggers a cascade of metabolic and vascular disorders that cause the development of DPN. In this regard, the first priority in the treatment of DPN should be normalization of glycemic levels. In this regard, of great interest is the use of pharmacopuncture, which has the largest range of biological effects: vasodilating, anti-inflammatory, increasing muscle strength, reducing the asymmetry of tendon reflexes, regenerating, antispasmodic effects. Pharmacopuncture is a method based on the injection of various agents, mainly medications, into the area of reflexology points in order to achieve a therapeutic effect for various nosological forms. Clinical data on the use of pharmacopuncture with nivalin in the treatment of diabetic polyneuropathy (DPN) in patients aged 35 to 60 years with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) are presented. Pharmacopuncture was used 6 times a week on the distal parts of the lower extremities, the course of treatment was 20-25 procedures. The presented material is the result of our own research, based on the use of a "model" of neurodegenerative pathology.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus, diabetic polyneuropathy, pharmacopuncture, nivalin.

УМИРОВА Сурайё Мамуржонова
PhD

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

КОРРЕКЦИЯ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ПОЛИНЕЙРОПАТИИ НИВАЛИНОМ С МЕТОДОМ ФАРМАКОПУНКТУРЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена коррекции диабетической полинейропатии методом фармакопунктуры – способа, базирующегося на введении медикаментов в область точек рефлексотерапии.

Диабетическая нейропатия, как и собственно сахарный диабет, приводит к значимым изменениям в жизни и здоровье пациентов. В основе формирования ДПН лежит прогрессирующая потеря миелинизированных волокон – сегментарная демиелинизация и аксональная дегенерация, вследствие которых нарушаются процессы проведения импульсов по нервному волокну. Гипергликемия запускает каскад метаболических и сосудистых нарушений, вызывающих развитие ДПН. В связи с этим первоочередной задачей в лечении ДПН должна быть нормализация уровня гликемии. В этом плане большой интерес представляет использование фармакопунктуры, обладающего наибольшим набором биологических эффектов: сосудорасширяющее, противовоспалительное, увеличение мышечной силы, уменьшении асимметрии сухожильных рефлексов, регенерирующее, спазмолитическое действие. Фармакопунктура представляет собой метод, базирующийся на инъекции различных агентов, преимущественно медикаментов, в область точек рефлексотерапии с целью достижения лечебного эффекта при различных нозологических формах. Представлены клинические данные по применению фармакопунктура с нивалином в лечении диабетической полинейропатии (ДПН) у больных в возрасте от 35 до 60 лет с сахарным диабетом (СД) 2 типа. Фармакопунктуры применяли в неделю 6 раза на дистальные отделы нижних конечностей, курс лечения составлял 20-25 процедур. Использование фармакопунктура с нивалином указанных параметров у больных с ДПН привело к улучшению клинических показателей нейропатии и позволило увеличить проводимость периферических нервов в 2-2,5 раза от исходных значений, что было подтверждено данными электромиографии. Представленный материал является результатом собственных исследований, построенных на использовании «модели» нейродегенеративной патологии.

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет, диабетическая полинейропатия, фармакопунктура нивалин.

UMIROVA Surayyo Mamurjonovna
PhD
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

FARMAKOPUNKTURA USULI ORQALI NIVALIN BILAN DIABETIK POLINEYROPATIYANI KORREKSIYALASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqola diabetik polineyropatiyani farmakopunktura usuli bilan davolashga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, bu usul refleksogen nuqtalar sohasiga dori-darmonlarni kiritishga asoslangan. Diabetik polineyropatiya ham, diabetning o'zi kabi, bemorlarning hayoti va sog'lig'ida sezilarli o'zgarishlarga olib keladi. DPN shakllanishi miyelini nerv tolalarining progressiv yo'qolishiga asoslanadi - segmentar demiyelinizatsiya va aksonal degeneratsiya natijasida nerv tolasi bo'ylab impulslarni uzatish jarayonlari buziladi. Giperglikemiya DPN rivojlanishiga sabab bo'lgan metabolik va qon-tomir buzilishlar kaskadini qo'zg'atadi. Shu munosabat bilan, DPNni davolashda birinchi navbatda glikemiyaning normallashtirish kerak bo'ladi. Shu sababli eng katta biologik ta'sir doirasiga ega bo'lgan farmakopunkturaga bugungi kunda qiziqishlar katta. Farmakopunktura-tomirlarni kengaytiruvchi, yallig'lanishga qarshi, mushaklar kuchini oshirish, pay reflekslarining assimetriyasini kamaytirish, regeneratsiya qiluvchi, antispazmolitik ta'sirga ega. Bu usul turli xil nozologik shakllar uchun terapevtik ta'sirga erishishda dori-darmonlarni refleksogen nuqtalar sohasiga kiritishga asoslangan. 2-toifa qandli diabeti (QD) mavjud 35 yoshdan 60 yoshgacha bo'lgan bemorlarda diabetik polineyropatiyani (DPN) davolashda nivalin bilan farmakopunkturadan foydalanish bo'yicha klinik ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Oyoqlarning distal qismlariga haftada 6 marta farmakopunktura usuli qo'llanilgan, davolash kursi 20-25 ta muolajani tashkil etgan. DPN bilan og'rikan bemorlarda nivalin bilan farmakopunkturadan foydalanish neyropatiyaning klinik ko'rsatkichlarining yaxshilanishiga olib keldi va periferik nervlarning o'tkazuvchanligini dastlabki qiymatlardan 2-2,5 baravar oshirishga imkon berdi, bu elektromiyografiya ma'lumotlari bilan ham tasdiqlangan. Taqdim etilgan material neyrodegenerativ patologiyaning "modeli" dan foydalanishga asoslangan o'z tadqiqotimiz natijasidir.

Kalit so'zlar: qandli diabet, diabetik polineuropatiya, farmakopunktura, nivalin.

Kirish: Hozirgi vaqtda butun dunyoda diabet bilan og'riqan bemorlar soni keskin o'sib bormoqda. Xalqaro qandli diabet federatsiyasining hisob-kitoblariga ko'ra, dunyo bo'ylab 425 million odam qandli diabetga chalingan va bu XXI asrning eng yirik global epidemiyasiga aylandi. Xitoyda 115 million, Hindistonda 73 million va AQShda 30 million odam qandli diabetga chalingan. Diabetik polinevropatiya (DPN) markaziy va periferik asab tizimidagi neyronlarning keng tarqalgan neyrodegenerativ kasalligi bo'lib, unda sezuvchi aksonlar, avtonom aksonlar, keyin esa, kamroq darajada, birinchi navbatda, motor aksonlari degeneratsiyalanadi. Qandli diabetda sezuvchi neyronlarning aniq qanday zararlanishi haqidagi savol munozarali bo'lib qolmoqda. Progressiv diabetik neyropatiya aksonlarning periferik qismini shikastlaydi va perikariyani (hujayra tanalarini) nisbatan tejab, ularning "o'lishi" ga olib keladi. Ko'pgina tadqiqotlar natijalariga ko'ra, diabetga chalingan har ikkinchi bemorda DPN belgilari mavjud. Neyropatiyaning "paypoq va qo'lqop" turlari eng uzun sezgi aksonlarning shikastlanishini aks ettiradi, masalan, oyoqda distal epidermal aksonlar proksimal epidermal aksonlaridan oldin shikastlanadi va shuning uchun diabetik polineuropatiya ham uzunlikka bog'liq neyropatiya hisoblanadi. Diabetik polineuropatiya demiyelinizatsiyalanuvchi neyropatiya hisoblanmasa ham, surunkali giperglikemiya natijasida Shwann hujayralari nishonga aylanadi. Shuning uchun diabetik neyropatiyaning og'ir shakllari bo'lgan bemorlarda demiyelinatsiya belgilari namoyon bo'ladi. 2,8-11,2% hollarda periferik asab tizimining zararlanishi bemorlarda prediabetning klinik belgilari yetarli darajada baholanmaganda aniqlanadi. Mualliflarning fikriga ko'ra, 1-toifa diabet bilan DPNning klinik belgilari tashxis qo'yilgandan 5 yil o'tgach paydo bo'la boshlaydi, QDning 2 turi mavjud bemorlarning 8-30% hollarda DPN aniqlanadi. DPN ning klinik xususiyatlari sezuvchanlik va vosita kasalliklari bo'lgan bemorlarda, shuningdek, reflekslardagi o'zgarishlarda namoyon bo'ladi. DPN ning dastlabki bosqichlarida harakat buzilishlari kam uchraydi. Oyoq reflekslaridagi o'zgarishlar, ayniqsa Axill refleksining kamayishi yoki yo'qolishi DPNning dastlabki belgisidir va asoratlar mavjudligining asosiy ko'rsatkichidir. Sensor buzilishlar katta va kichik nerv tolalari zararlanganda, tebranish va proprioseptiv sezuvchanlik pasayadi. DPNni kompleks davolashda farmakopunktura - eng zamonaviy va samarali davolash usullaridan biri bo'lib, refleksologiya va gomeopatiyani o'zida birlashtiradi. Gomeopatik dori-darmonlarni akupunktura nuqtalariga kiritish orqali ikkinchisini rag'batlantirishga erishiladi. Aslida, bu nuqtalarni rag'batlantirish usullaridan biri bo'lib, energiya aylanishini, butun organizmning funksional faoliyatini tartibga solishga, uning fiziologik funksiyalarini normallashtirishga imkon beradi.

Maqsad 2-toifa qandli diabet bilan og'riqan bemorlarda DPNni davolashda nivalin bilan farmakopunktura usulining samaradorligini o'rganish.

Tadqiqot materiali va usullari. 2-toifa qandli diabet bilan kasallangan 35 yoshdan 60 yoshgacha bo'lgan 75 nafar bemor (35 ta erkak va 40 ta ayol) kuzatuv ostiga olindi. Qandli diabetning o'rtacha davomiyligi bemorlarda 2 yildan 12 yilgacha tashkil etdi. Tadqiqotga qo'shilish mezonini bu bemorlarda DPN mavjudligi edi. Deyarli barcha bemorlar dekompensatsiyalangan diabet bosqichida edi; HbA1c darajasi 8,7-11,6% oralig'ida bo'ldi. Periferik asab tizimidagi o'zgarishlar ob'ektiv belgilar yordamida neyropatik disfunktsional ball - NDS shkalasi yordamida baholandi, bu taktil, og'riq va harorat sezgirligini o'rganish natijalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Bundan tashqari, quyidagi ENMG ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha ham baholandi: M-javobning amplitudasi (mV), impuls o'tkazuvchanligi tezligi (ISV, m/s), qoldiq kechikish qiymati (RL, m/s), sezgi potensialining amplitudasi (PD, mV). Taktil sezuvchanlik 10 grammlik monofilament paxta yordamida, og'riq sezuvchanligi igna yordamida, harorat sezuvchanligi «Thio-Therm» asbobi yordamida, reflekslar esa odatiy tarzda aniqlandi. ENMG Neuro-EMG-Micro-2 (Rossiya) apparatida amalga oshirildi. Neyropatiyaning bosqichlari esa P. Dyck va P. Thomas (1999) tomonidan taklif qilingan tasnifga [8] muvofiq baholandi (1-jadval).

1-jadval.

Diabetik polineuropatiyaning bosqichlari

DPN bosqichi	Xarakterli belgilari
--------------	----------------------

0-bosqich	DPN belgilari rivojlanmagan yoki yo‘q, vegetativ testlar manfiy, motor va sezgi periferik nervlarning ENMG tekshiruvi (bir tomondan kamida ikkitasi) hech qanday patologiyani ko‘rsatmaydi.
1-bosqich - subklinik (1a, 1b)	1a - DPNning alomatlari yoki ob‘ektiv nevrologik belgilari yo‘q; bir tomondan motor va sezgi nervlarni ENMGda o‘rganish paytida aniqlangan har qanday ikkita o‘zgarishlarning kombinatsiyasi mavjud bo‘ladi; 1b – DPN alomatlari yo‘q; klinik tekshiruv bir tomondan DPNning ikki yoki undan ortiq ob‘ektiv nevrologik belgilarini aniqlaydi.
2-bosqich - klinik (2a, 2b)	2a - DPN uchun xarakterli shikoyatlar; sezgi, harakat, vegetativ buzilishlar, oyoq fleksorlarining zaiflik belgilarisiz (bemor tovonida bemalol turishi mumkin); 2b - bir xil + oyoq fleksorlarining zaifligi belgilari (bemor tovonida turolmaydi)
3-bosqich - og‘ir	Mehnat qobiliyatining yo‘qolishi bilan kechuvchi neyropatiya

Farmakopunktura oyoqlarning distal qismlarida haftasiga 6 marta 0,2-0,3 ml hajmda nivalinni refleksogen nuqtalar sohasida teri ostiga yuborish orqali amalga oshirildi. Bitta muolaja davomida nuqtalarga jami taxminan 2 ml preparat kiritildi, bu bitta ampulaning hajmiga teng, davolash kursi 20-25 ta muolajadan iborat bo‘ldi.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Barcha 75 nafar bemorlarda davo muolajasini qabul qilishdan oldin oyoqlarda charchoq hissi, jismoniy faollikdan keyin kechqurun oyoqlarda o‘rtacha, epizodik og‘riqlar va - 41 (43%) nafar bemorda, paresteziya - 29 (31%) nafarida, oyoqlarning uvishishi va kuyish hissinig bo‘lishiga 25 (26%) nafar bemorlar shikoyat qildilar. Oyoqlarda sezgining buzilishi ko‘rinishlari sifatida harorat sezgisining buzilishi - 66 (91%) nafar bemorlarda, og‘riq sezgisining bo‘lishi - 63 (77%), taktil sezuvchanlik buzilishi - 14 (15%), Axill reflekslarining pasayishi - 56 (59%), hamda tizza reflekslarining pasayishi - 34 (36%) nafar bemorlarda aniqlandi. NDS shkalasi bo‘yicha ob‘ektiv nevrologik simptomlarning miqdoriy o‘rtacha ko‘rsatkichi $7,2 \pm 2,8$ ballni tashkil etdi. ENMG tekshiruvda bemorlarning 84% da surunkali demiyelinatsiyalanuvchi distal sensomotor neyropatiya belgilari aniqlangan. ENMGni baholashda o‘zgarishlar ko‘pincha motor nervida n. peroneusda (58 bemorda) aniqlangan. M-javob amplitudasining pasayishi shaklida (52 nafar bemorda), kamroq – IO‘T (42 nafar bemorda), RL osishi (36 nafar bemorda) kuzatilgan. N.tibialis bo‘yicha ENMG ko‘rsatkichlarining o‘zgarishi 58 ta bemorda M-javob amplitudasining pasayishi (64 ta bemorda), kamroq darajada, IO‘T (43 nafar bemorda) va RL ning oshishi (38 nafar bemorda) aniqlandi. N.suralisni stimulyatsiya qilishda sezuvchanlik (sezgir) potentsialning pasayishi ancha kam - 29 nafar bemorda kuzatilgan (1-rasm). Barcha bemorlarda ikki yoki undan ortiq o‘rganilgan parametrlarda o‘zgarishlarni ko‘rsatdilar.

1-rasm. Davolashdan oldin DPN va ENMG ko‘rsatkichlarining namoyon bo‘lish dinamikasi

Tekshiruv natijasida 23 (24%) nafar bemorlarda 1b bosqichdagi DPN, 2a bosqichi – 46 (49%) ta bemorda; 2b-bosqichdagi DPN – 26 (27%) nafar bemorlarda aniqlandi.

Nivalin preparati bilan farmakopunktura samaradorligini baholash uchun barcha bemorlar 2 guruhga bo‘lib o‘rganildi: 1-guruhga gipoglikemik doti vositalarini qabul qiluvch bazis terapiyadagi 50 nafar bemorlar kiritilgan; 2-guruh 45 nafar bemorlardan iborat bo‘lib, ular uglevod almashinuviga ta’sir etuvchi dori vositalari bilan birga oyoqlarning distal qismiga Nivalin preparati bilan farmakopunktura muolajasini qabul qilishdi.

Davolash samaradorligining natijalari 1 oydan keyin 2 ta tadqiqot guruhida ham baholandi. 1-guruhda bemorlarning aksariyati hali ham shikoyatlar va sezgi buzilishlarga ega edi; NDS shkalasi bo‘yicha umumiy ball $5,3 \pm 1,7$ ballni tashkil etdi (dastlabki $7,2 \pm 2,8$ ballga nisbatan). DPNni davolashda nivalin bilan farmakopunktura buyurilgan 2-guruh bemorlarda sezilarli ijobiy dinamika

qayd etildi. Deyarli barcha bemorlar oyoqlarda og‘riqning pasayishini qayd etdilar. NDS shkalasi bo‘yicha sezgi o‘zgarishlarini baholashda umumiy ball $4,2 \pm 0,8$ ballni tashkil etdi ($p < 0,05$), asosan harorat sezgisining yaxshilanishi (63 nafar bemorda) va og‘riqning pasayishi (54 nafar bemorda) qayd etildi.

2-jadval.

Davolanishdan 1 oydan keying DPN belgilari va ENMG ko‘rsatkichlarining namoyon bo‘lish dinamikasi

Ko‘rsatkichlar	Kuzatish vaqti	Dastlab	1 oydan keyin	
			1-guruh	2-guruh
Ob‘ektiv belgilarni baholash	NDS, ball	$7,2 \pm 2,8$	$5,3 \pm 1,7$	$4,2 \pm 0,8^*$
ENMG ko‘rsatkichlari	M-javob, mV	$1,3 \pm 0,4$	$1,6 \pm 1,8$	$3,4 \pm 0,5^*$
	IO‘T, m/s	$36,9 \pm 1,6$	$37,8 \pm 3,4$	$56,7 \pm 1,4^*$
	RL, m/s	$5,4 \pm 1,0$	$4,6 \pm 1,4$	$3,2 \pm 0,9^*$

* $p < 0,05$; ** $p < 0,01$ davolashdan oldingi qiymatlar bilan solishtirilganda

ENMG tekshiruvi 1 oydan keyin takrorlanganda, dastlabki ma‘lumotlarga nisbatan ijobiy dinamika faqat 2-guruh bemorlarda IO‘T ning oshishi ($36,3$ m/s ga nisbatan $56,7$ m/s), M-javob parametrlarining normallasishi ($1,3$ mV ga nisbatan $3,4$ mV), RL ning pasayishi ($3,4$ m/s ga nisbatan $5,1$ m/s) kuzatildi, natijalar 2-jadvalda keltirilgan.

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, nivalin bilan farmakopunkturadan foydalanish periferik nerv impulslarining o‘tkazuvchanligini dastlabki qiymatlardan 2-2,5 barobar oshirish imkonini berdi. Ushbu usulning mavjudligi 2-toifa diabet bilan og‘rigan bemorlarda DPNni kompleks davolashda foydalanishni tavsiya qilish imkonini beradi.

IQTIBOSLAR | ЧОККИ | REFERENCES:

1. Agasarov L.G., Belyaeva E.A. Particular issues of antihomotoxic therapy // Clinical medicine and pharmacology. 2017;3(2). 31–33. (in Russ).
2. Agasarov L.G. Reflexology for common diseases of the nervous system. M., 2017; 240. (in Russ).
3. Kersshot Ya. Clinical guide to biopuncture. Per. from English M.: Arnebia, 2013;224. (in Russ).
4. Kamalova Y. A., Umirova S. M., Naimova H. A. The influence of various dosing methods on the physical performance of children in the city of Samarkand // Materials of the XXIII Congress of the Physiological Society named after. IP Pavlova with international participation. 2017; 2248-2250. (in Russ).
5. Matmurodov R.J., Umirova S.M., The role of coronavirus infection in the development of diabetic polyneuropathies and its effect on the complement system // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2021;6(3):256-263. (in Uzb)
6. Matmurodov R.J., Umirova S.M., Comparative analysis of clinical-neurological, neurophysiological disorders and complement C3 component in patients with diabetic polyneuropathy who underwent Covid-19 // Journal of neurology and neurosurgery research. №3-2023; 51-55. (in Uzb)
7. Mavlyanova Z. F. Reflexotherapy and aromatherapy in the treatment of patients with discirculatory encephalopathy // Modern pharmacy: problems and development prospects. 2015;428-431. (in Russ).
8. Khalimova H.M., Matmurodov R.J., Umirova S.M., Assessment of the dynamics of diabetic polyneuropathies in patients with Covid-19 // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2023;8(3):310-314. (in Uzb)

9. Matmurodov RJ, Umirova SM. Results of the use of combilepene tabsa in the treatment of diabetic polyneuropathy in young people // Journal of cardiorespiratory research. 2021;1. (in Russ).
10. Mavlyanova Z. F. Reflexotherapy and aromatherapy in the treatment of patients with discirculatory encephalopathy //Modern pharmacy: problems and development prospects. 2015; 428-431. (in Russ).
11. Umirova SM, Matmurodov RJ. Features of early diagnosis and treatment of the diabetic polyneuropathy in adults. medicine new day _ Avicenna-med. uz. 2022;6:44. (in Uzb)
12. Abdullaev R. B. Features of the clinical course, prevalence and new approaches to the treatment of peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum in the Southern Aral Sea region // Author's ANNOTATION. diss.... doc. honey. Sci. 2002:15-23. (in Russ).
13. Abdullaev R. B., Yakubova A. B. Chronicle hepatitis (the spread of the disease and its treatment in Zhanubiy Arol byi, which is considered an ecologist unfavorable // Khorazm Publishing House Urganch.2008. (in Uzb)
14. Matmurodov RJ, Umirova SM. The role of coronavirus infection in the development of diabetic polyneuropathy and its effect on the complement system // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice.2021;6.
15. Sharafova I. A. et al. Kinesiotaping: New Look at the Rehabilitation of Facial Nerve Neuropathy in Children //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. 2021:4763-4768.
16. Kamalova Y. A., Dzhumanov Zh. A. The importance of therapeutic exercises in the complex of methods of physical rehabilitation of patients with osteochondrosis of the lumbar spine // Bulletin of Science and Education. 2020; 23-3 (101): 66-70. (in Russ).
17. Baratova S., Mavlyanova Z., Sharafova I. Study of the temperament of female athletes involved in taekwondo // Doctor's Bulletin Journal. 2019;1(2): 30-32. (in Russ).
18. Anatolevna, Kim Olga, Abdusalomova Maftuna Akbarovna, and Makhmudov Sardor Mamasharifovich. "Zhalolitdinova Shaxnoza Akbarzhon kizi, & Ibragimova Leyla Ilxomovna, the influence of risk factors on the development of cerebral strokes in children. open access repository. 2022;8 (04): 179–182. (in Russ).

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 5

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000